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Analysis of public transport in Vienna with Co2 emissions in Austria's households

PTCO2

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Analysis of public transport in Vienna with Co2 emissions in Austria's household project, delivered in April 2024. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the FAIR data section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Theresa Bodner will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Two datasets are reused for the analysis. "Verkehrsmittelwahl Wien" is annually published by Stadt Wien. The data is obtained and made available by Wiener Linien.

"Carbon footprints" is published by Eurostat, the statistical office of the EU.

The analysis will mainly produce two csv datasets and additional plots to display the results. We want to investigate the means of transport in Vienna in the timeframe 2010 to 2021. Moreover, we look at the Co2 emissions of Austrian households in the same time period. Lastly, we want to set the bicycle usage in correlation to the Co2 emissions.

The results of the analysis give insights into the developments of transport usage in Vienna and Co2 emissions and are relevant for everybody who wants to investigate these connections.

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	result_data.csv	Structured text	csv	< 50 KB	no
P2	transport_emission.png	Images	png	< 50 KB	no
P3	emissions_data.csv	Structured text	csv	< 50 KB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P4	correlation.png	Images	png	< 50 KB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Verkehrsmittelwahl Wien	https://www.wien.gv.at/stadtentwicklung/energie/ogd/verkehrsmittelwahl2021.csv	CC-BY-4.0	no
R2	Carbon footprints	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/api/dissemination/sdmx/2.1/data/env_ac_co2fp?format=TSV&compressed=true	CC-BY-4.0	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

As a first step, the datasets are downloaded for the respective sources and then filtered for the relevant data. We are only interested in numbers from the years 2010 to 2021. For the "Verkehrsmittelwahl Wien" dataset we filter for CAR, BICYCLE, BY_FOOT and PUBLIC_TRANSPORT in the specified time range.

The "Carbon footprints" dataset is given as an archive file and has to be unzipped first. Then it has to be transformed from tsv to csv format for easier computation. Moreover, we are only interested in data from Austrian households. These steps are all done automatically when running the Python file filter.py.

filter.py transforms and generates the desired output files, emissions_data.csv and result_data.csv. In a further step, the results are displayed as plots with the Python program visualise.py, which outputs transport_emission.png and correlation.png.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community, students, and everybody who is interested in research about public transport usage in Vienna and Co2 emissions can reuse the data.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The data as well as the source code are uploaded to GitHub, which handles the versioning. The folder input holds all the input data, in the output folder we find all the produced data and the figures.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. It can be found in the main folder on GitHub and explains all the fields of the data input and output tables. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data. Additionally, there are instructions on how to run the programs and produce the output again.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if

opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. During the project phase, the data as well as the source code are documented and versioned via GitHub licensed with MIT license.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-04-25	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.11068518	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open		2024-04-25	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.11068518	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open		2024-04-25	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.11068518	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open		2024-04-25	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.11068518	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster.

Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com/TheresaBo/DataStewProject>

Methods or software needed to access and use data:

The input and output .csv files can be opened and viewed with a spreadsheet program like Excel.

The result .png figures can be viewed with any image viewer.

Python 3.9.7 has been used for the programs filter.py and visualise.py. Pandas and matplotlib are used libraries which can be installed via pip install. The GitHub repository can be cloned to the local machine to run the programs locally. For view the program source code, any IDE or text editor can be used, e.g. PyCharm or VSCode.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets. The descriptions for the datasets can be found in the README file in the GitHub repository.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

The following data quality checks will be done: data entry validation.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

The Python programs (filter.py, visualize.py) used to generate the output are published on GitHub (<https://github.com/TheresaBo/DataStewProject>).

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are **no** costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with Theresa Bodner being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

All essential files can be found in the GitHub repository, which can be found under the link: <https://github.com/TheresaBo/DataStewProject>

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

During the project phase P2 (transport_emission.png), P4 (correlation.png), P1 (result_data.csv), R1 (Verkehrsmittelwahl Wien), R2 (Carbon footprints), P3 (emissions_data.csv) will be stored on GitHub.

As backup and long-term preservation, the output data of the analysis will be uploaded to a Zenodo repository. (10.5281/zenodo.11068163)

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by Theresa Bodner who is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	Zenodo	10 years
P2	Zenodo	10 years
P3	Zenodo	10 years
P4	Zenodo	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?